

Bridging Knowledge Gaps: The Potential of MOOCs for Political Science Education

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Abstract. The increasing demand for political knowledge and skills, driven by upskilling and reskilling, makes Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) a strategic tool for improving the global relevance of Political science education. This paper analyzes the IPSAMOOC project, which offers an introductory cluster of seven political science courses, delivered on Coursera and edX. Using survey responses, the study aims at examining profiles of “engaged” learners, their experience with courses, their motivation for participation, and their overall perception of the potential impact of political science education through MOOCs. The results confirm a growing international interest in the field and a high level of awareness among the involved learners. Indeed, MOOCs are identified as an effective tool to address widespread training demands, supporting academic and professional growth, and as a tool for expanding access to Political science education, especially in underserved regions such as the Global South, and supporting global SDGs. In this regard, MOOCs appear to be a valuable hub for political science university initiatives to achieve learning and civic goals and widen the disciplinary dissemination impact.

Keywords: MOOCs, Political science education, Professional & civic development, Global south.

1 Scaling Political Science Education with MOOCs

In the fifteen years since the first MOOCs were offered, the landscape of digital learning has undergone profound changes from digitalization to AI [1], marked by the escalating processes of “datafication” and “marketisation” within higher education [2] [3], which posed major challenges to the university-led model of massiveness and openness of MOOCs. Nevertheless, the resilience of the format and the strategic vision of the institutions involved have ensured its continued relevance. Despite being declared too early obsolete [4] [5], MOOCs still occupy a central role in the multifaceted landscape of online education for at least two main reasons. Firstly, the “normalization” of their use. MOOCs, with their structured design, high-quality content, and usability, confirm to serve as a versatile format for diverse training strategies [6]. Moreover, the pandemic accelerated their adoption, prompting institutions to implement fully remote or blended learning models, and “even those [institutions] who were reluctant to adapt have had to

accept the use of distance-learning tools [...], and the result is a rather multifaceted world of teaching approaches” [7] [8]. Secondly, the key factors behind MOOCs’ success have not lost their strength over time [9] [10]. These include the provision of affordable, high-quality content; the removal of geographical barriers; accessible learning opportunities that contribute to the empowerment of citizens; and the development of skills aligned with evolving labor market demands.

Building on these strengths, political science is uniquely positioned to capitalize on the potential of MOOCs, in the light of the discipline’s global scope and interdisciplinary approach. As political knowledge becomes increasingly relevant in addressing contemporary challenges related to digitalization [11] [12] and consolidated local development issues [13], MOOCs offer an effective means of enhancing flexible and open access to learning content, and the professional applicability of political science education [14]. However, while research on MOOCs continues to attract the interest of scholars [15], the extant literature and experience still offers limited insights into their effectiveness and impact within this specific domain [16] [17]. Existing research on the teaching of political science has focused predominantly on the differences between online and in-person education, yielding conflicting results [18-22]. Instead, less attention has been paid to exploring the extent to which the massive and asynchronous nature of MOOCs may at least partially escape this dichotomy, as they are widely seen as effective tools for achieving both personal and collective goals. This may be particularly relevant for learners in the field. MOOCs have been recognized as ‘the most appropriate element to fulfil the civic mission of disseminating, studying and deepening democratic values’ [23], a concept which is particularly relevant to the Global South [24] [25]. Moreover, individual mechanisms and meanings behind learner behavior in MOOCs remain largely unexplored [26]. The IPSAMOOC project fits into this context. Based on a collaboration between the International Political Science Association (IPSA) and Federica WebLearning, the distance learning center of the University of Naples, the IPSAMOOC project promoted the publication of seven introductory courses covering key areas of political science, including comparative politics, international relations and political theory¹. Strengthening IPSA’s strategic goals², MOOCs are aligned within a global framework characterized by growing attention to the United Nations’ Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). To this end, the courses have been created with an attention to the accessibility of learning content and to the potential international need for lifelong learning and published on the main international platforms to take advantage of the growing recognition of their certifications. In fact, while MOOCs have been pioneering the process of “microcredentialisation” since their early stages, it is only recently that the interest of private technology firms seems to have led academic institutions to see nano and micro

¹ Courses: 1. Comparative Political Systems; 2. Comparative Research Designs and Methods; 3. Contemporary Issues in World Politics; 4. Democracy and Autocracy; 5. Global Politics; 6. Introducción a la teoría política; 7. Understanding Political Concepts.

² IPSA: Strategic plan 2023-2027, <https://u.garr.it/a75tB>, last accessed 2025/02/20.

credentials as a way to attract career-focused learners and boost institutions' role in linking academia and industry globally³.

This study seeks to begin to analyze the extent to which political science MOOCs – within the traditional self-paced MOOC model, which remains the most scalable form of online education used by higher education institutions – can contribute to achieving these goals. To this end, in the following sections we will present the results of an exploratory survey, aimed at better understanding the profile and motivation, and gathering feedback from a group of “engaged” learners. The paragraphs will focus on four main aspects, corresponding to the sections into which the questionnaire was divided: their profile, to assess the characteristics of these learners; their experiences with the courses, to gather feedback on the perceived quality and effectiveness of the content and delivery format; the learners' motivations for participating in the courses and their takeaways; and their overall perceptions of the value of learning the discipline via MOOC.

2 Scaling Political Science Education with MOOCs

The global audience of IPSAMOOCs, from its launch in 2018 to December 2024, includes a widely distributed learner base, with an almost even split between those living in fully or flawed democracies (mostly from the most populous, i.e. the US and India) and non-democratic contexts (as classified by The Economist Intelligence Unit, 2024). Over 40% of the learners, are from the Global South, indicating a strong interest in political science education in this region and a critical need for specialized, high-quality education. Second, the educational background shows that the majority of IPSAMOOC learners have at least a bachelor's degree, even if a quarter have a secondary education, suggesting that the project is reaching out beyond traditionally academically educated audiences. This heterogeneous learner population forms the sampling frame for the exploratory study on active learners, which was conducted through a survey administered between December 21, 2024 and January 10, 2025 and received 307 responses from “engaged” learners who voluntarily participated in the survey and explicitly expressed their interest in being part of a learning community for future interactions and participation in initiatives.

The profile of respondents matches the expectations of an active MOOC audience of lifelong learners: spread across demographic sections, with a good level of education, literacy and access to digital environments; familiar with online learning. All age groups are represented, albeit with a decreasing trend with increasing age, with one third of respondents falling in the 20-30 age group and around 20% in the 31-40 age group. Similarly, the gender distribution appears to be in line with the overall demographic composition of the wider MOOC audience, with a slight majority of men represented (at least 55% on average). In terms of previous education, a significant proportion of respondents on both platforms (over 80%) have at least one higher

³ Coursera global skills report 2024, <https://u.garr.it/ky618>, last accessed 2025/02/20.

education qualification, with the majority split between those with a Bachelor's degree (36%) and those with a Master's degree (35%).

This is consistent with the demographics of a higher education level audience, but also with expectations of possible public interest in political science and with a rational use of online learning. The profile of lifelong learners is confirmed by their positioning on the student-worker continuum, since while the majority of respondents identify themselves mainly as workers or students (more than 65%, with a similar distribution), a proportion (almost 20%) identify themselves as neither students nor workers, thus suggesting their use of MOOCs as an orientation tool and transition support. The geographical distribution shows a diversified audience, with more than 60 different countries represented, and a broad regional distribution, underlining the capacity of political science courses to attract interest far beyond the Western world. The significant representation of participants from the Global South underlines their potential to function as a global and inclusive platform, promoting broader access to knowledge in the field across different regions and the related responsibility to deepen thematic and implementation needs.

Two elements of regional distribution seem interesting to complete the profile of these users. The first is the dual perception of access. While the vast majority of respondents report having good or excellent skills, extensive access to the internet and the ability to afford it, around 20% of them feel that internet access is still too expensive for everyone to have access. This suggests that factors that are often seen as barriers to MOOC participation – such as computer skills, internet access and affordability of connectivity – are relatively minor concerns for this sample, but are identified by respondents as contextual factors that exacerbate inequalities in access for the population as a whole. The second is the confirmation of a different habit in terms of access to online courses. The analysis of device usage highlights the general consistency with MOOC usage, with a strong preference for portable (almost half of respondents) and desktop (around a third) computers in all regions, with significant minorities preferring access via mobile phones (18%) and tablets (5%). However, half of mobile phone users are concentrated in South Asia and sub-Saharan Africa, where tablet use is also widespread.

Finally, their use of MOOCs confirms their “engaged” nature as learners with significant prior MOOC experience. Most respondents reported having taken several MOOCs, with two-thirds having completed at least two prior to the one for which they received the survey invitation; and the majority took more than one of the seven political science courses offered.

3 Learning Experience: Looking for Quality Contents, Community and AI Support

In terms of satisfaction and perceived usefulness, the courses met users' expectations. The responses show a consistently positive reception, with over 95% of learners rating the course as “excellent” or “good”, indicating a general appreciation of the learning experience, both for the course as a whole – interest in the subject and quality of

teaching – and for the composition of the materials available. Predictably, the most valued feature is video lectures, with more than 60% of respondents at both Coursera and edX finding them to be the most useful element of the learning experience. This is consistent with the nature of MOOCs, which prioritize accessible and engaging video content to facilitate self-paced learning. However, in descending order, readings were also highly valued, contrary to the main guidelines for MOOC development and the most visible trend on the major platforms. This is an important feature of the design of these courses, for which the presence of a significant set of texts and links to readings, selected from open access repositories and, to a minimal extent, from repositories accessible via most university circuits, was considered a distinctive feature, offering the possibility of more in-depth study and contact with other indispensable methods of access to study and in-depth analysis. Captions, quizzes and assignments were valued more as a complementary tool for learning than as a value in themselves. Finally, external resources were considered “very useful” by around 40% of respondents on both platforms. Despite the overall positive reception of these design elements, further insights were gained through open-ended responses about potential areas for improvement. Learner spontaneous feedback was divided between those advocating for additional video lectures and those favoring more reading materials. Notably, few respondents from Sub-Saharan Africa and Latin America and the Caribbean emphasized the need for downloadable scripts and course resources for offline use and for translation of both video and text materials. Other important suggestions relate to the possibility of increasing student participation in “unexpected” ways, such as the inclusion of more complex evaluative or formative activities, such as written essays, and the establishment of a knowledge-sharing platform to promote intellectual exchange and community growth among IPSAMOOC learners.

Calls for greater integration of AI-based student support tools were also noted, particularly from respondents in the MENA region and Latin America and the Caribbean. AI literacy emerges as a key factor in online learning, despite the fact that many AI tools are not yet integrated or have only recently been introduced in MOOC environments. The data shows that a significant portion of respondents relied on AI tools to enhance their learning experience. Given the different integration of AI in the two platforms, with a very focused structuring of Coursera’s chatbot, the questions aimed to uncover the main functions for which users had used AI tools, either internal or external to the platform. The most frequently cited use was the generation of real-life examples related to course topics, highlighting the value of AI in making theoretical knowledge more practical and applicable. However, slightly less prominent but equally important functions were reported: Coursera respondents highlighted the use of AI tools to generate summaries, while edX learners reported a greater focus on creating practice questions, reflecting their emphasis on reinforcement and self-assessment. Interestingly, nearly 20% of respondents from Coursera courses had used the platform’s recently released internal chatbot (in fact, a third of them were still unaware of it), finding it a useful tool for all available functions: to better understand complex course concepts or topics, get help with quizzes or assignments, find additional resources or references related to the course material, translate content or understand the course in a

non-native language, contribute to discussion forums, or generate ideas for participation.

Overall, the feedback confirms the value of traditional course components and the need for further research to improve them and confirms AI as the main challenge for MOOC development. The findings highlight the flexibility of AI-enhanced functions to meet different learning needs and suggest that it is already widely used as a tool to deepen conceptual understanding and enrich guided and autonomous learning, which is likely to help improve retention and learning performance.

4 Learner Motivation: Political Science for Professional Development

Personal and professional development emerge as the main reasons for enrolling in a political science course. Around 20% of respondents indicated that they had enrolled on the course mainly to fulfil academic study objectives, while over 25% indicated professional development as their main objective; within this, around 50% of respondents indicated that the main impact of completing the course was to contribute to their continuing professional development (CPD) hours. In addition, about a quarter of respondents cited personal development as their main objective; with a higher percentage on edX, probably for reasons related to the platforms' access policies. In this case, the main perceived impact is directly related to the improved understanding of political science concepts. Elements such as the low cost of completion and the prestige of both the platform and the IPSA are considered secondary, but still relevant, with 7% and 5% of respondents respectively citing them as their primary motivation.

A significant level of motivation is confirmed by the choice of the enrollment option, where individual subscriptions predominate, indicating a high level of personal engagement. The individual subscription allows for the certificate, which about half of the learners have obtained, even if respondents report obtaining the certificate as a minority objective, suggesting that learners prioritize learning outcomes over credentials or external validation, in line with the profile of motivated, self-directed learners. The level of motivation is reinforced by the number of hours of study reported. Almost half of Coursera users spent 1-2 hours per week, and almost a third spent 3-4 hours per week, with the remaining 8% spending less than an hour. A similar trend is observed among edX learners, despite a greater share of audit-mode users.

The preference for individual enrollment is aligned with the mode of learning reported by respondents, which has been self-paced for around 90%. Furthermore, the fact – technical but not necessarily marginal – that the course was accessed mainly through the platform's internal search tool, i.e. by keyword or tag, confirms that this personal study program is part of habitual use of MOOCs for these learners.

Another useful pointer to understand learner motivation is the diverse topics of the MOOCs taken before the political science ones, and to the diverse backgrounds of the respondents – with less than half having a social science background, and the other half mostly split between humanities, economics and computer science. This data confirms the interdisciplinary interest in political science and suggests that these courses appeal

to individuals who are not primarily trained in social sciences. More specifically, among the non-social sciences respondents, a substantial proportion of respondents come from the arts & humanities (33.7%), while a significant presence also emerges from the STEM area with physical science & engineering and computer science & data science backgrounds (21.7% combined). This heterogeneity suggests that political science knowledge is indeed seen as a convergence point for individuals with diverse interests, underscoring the discipline's ability to embrace interdisciplinarity and to provide analytical tools and useful knowledge relevant to critically address real-world challenges.

Therefore, the learner motivation for professional development underscores the potential of political science education to address diverse professional needs, particularly in non-Western countries, highlighting the discipline's crucial role in meeting this demand.

5 Perceptions of Political Science Education through MOOCs

The perception of political science education through MOOCs was observed through the lens of the relationship that respondents identified between their course and IPSA's strategic goals and the UN's SDGs.

First, IPSA's strategic goals are directly related to the impact of political science on the development of scholars and citizens worldwide and on international academic cooperation. The first two areas in which respondents perceive that global distribution of online courses has the greatest impact is in "increasing outreach, visibility and reputability of political science research", with more than 20% of respondents identifying this as the primary contribution of the promotion of political science MOOCs, and "promoting the global standing of political science through enhanced outreach and knowledge dissemination", also identified by around 20% of respondents. This reflects the learners' recognition of the value of online learning and the educational initiative as a tool for the dissemination of the discipline, as also confirmed by the goal "foster scientific training and education in political science", which is third in the list of preference. This may also indicate that these objectives are perceived as closely related, if not overlapping. Additionally, the "promotion of academic freedom" is also acknowledged, with around 10% of learners identifying this as the main element of impact, indicating a shared perception of the IPSAMOOC as supporting the intellectual independence and integrity of political scientists. This perception appears particularly relevant for edX respondents from regions such as MENA and South Asia, where about 40% of respondents consider it a crucial strategic goal. The contribution to "equity, diversity, and inclusion" is also noteworthy, with more than 10% of respondents recognizing its role in fostering best practices within the discipline. This is particularly true for Global South learners, where our data reinforces the critical need for empowering underserved regions through human resource development, offering critical conceptual frameworks for political analysis, and cultivating the capacity to design effective policy responses to current and emergent challenges. Therefore, the perception of the IPSAMOOC project is that it not only fosters intellectual growth but

also promotes civic engagement and empowers individuals – and practitioners – to participate in shaping their political realities.

Second, learners also identified a direct link to the SDGs. The largest proportion (29%) selected goals related to “peace, justice, and strong institutions”, as well as “partnerships for the goals”, reflecting a clear alignment with the course focus on political science and governance. Another notable share (26%) highlighted “quality education, decent work”, and industry, innovation, and infrastructure, suggesting that participants also see the course as contributing to social and economic development objectives. In this sense, the IPSAMOOC project serves as a testament to the transformative potential of online education in bridging knowledge gaps and empowering individuals to become active agents of change. In contrast, “no poverty, reduced inequalities, and gender equality” (12%), along with categories linked to environmental sustainability and health (ranging from 8% to 9%), garnered smaller, though still meaningful, recognition. Taken together, these results imply that while learners recognize the IPSAMOOCs broad applicability to multiple sustainable development aims, they perceive its strongest impact in areas most directly related to political science, institutional capacity, and educational advancement.

Expanding on the analysis with a regional perspective, the data show that learners from nearly all areas primarily associate the IPSAMOOC with “peace, justice, and strong institutions and partnerships for the goals”. This is particularly evident in regions such as MENA, Sub-Saharan Africa, and Latin America & the Caribbean. A similar pattern emerges for “quality education, decent work, and Industry, innovation, and infrastructure”. By contrast, SDGs concerning poverty, inequality, and gender (e.g., “no poverty, reduced inequalities, gender equality”) see their highest mentions in MENA and Sub-Saharan Africa. Overall, these results confirm that while the IPSAMOOCs are broadly viewed as advancing multiple SDGs, learners especially recognize their contribution to the political, institutional, and educational dimensions of sustainable development.

6 Final Remarks

The growing multidisciplinary of the training needs of lifelong learners for personal and professional growth offers an opportunity for subject areas that are under-represented in the MOOC universe. The great success of the introductory courses in political science included in the IPSAMOOC project demonstrates the interest in the subject from a vast international audience. This exploratory analysis confirms the main considerations that guided the design of the courses and the initiative. Firstly, there is widespread interest in developing knowledge and skills in the field of political science, as evidenced by the demand for more training in specific areas, not only to support a course of study, but also for personal growth and, above all, professional and career development. Secondly, MOOCs are recognized as an educational tool that can help learners achieve their learning objectives, due to the quality of the content and, above all, the flexibility of access and use. The limitations related to the lack of interaction

are not seen as an obstacle, but as a critical issue to be worked on in order to find alternative solutions, which would for instance benefit from further AI integration, for engaging students through training activities of different formats and possible parallel community building initiatives. Thirdly, there is a general recognition of the value of teaching political science through MOOCs as a tool to achieve both personal and collective goals, with the strengthening of knowledge in the sector and research communities (SDGs and IPSA goals). Finally, the analysis confirms that “engaged” MOOC users tend to establish reinforcement and loyalty mechanisms on the international platforms. In this sense, the reflection suggests the need for a further commitment by organizations – universities and international academic associations – to increase the amount of content available and to define modes of action that allow a clearer identification of widespread needs and the definition of a response to the demand for interaction with the wider community. These preliminary conclusions are proposed as a starting point for further analysis aimed at defining an operational definition and planning new initiatives.

Acknowledgments. The authors thank IPSA and Federica WebLearning for their commitment to online learning in political science. Special thanks go to Federica Founder and President, Prof. Mauro Calise, and Director, Prof. Fortunato Musella, for their guidance of IPSAMOOC. This analysis was also carried out within the framework of the ALMA project (Advanced Learning Multimedia Alliance for Inclusive Academic Innovation), specifically as part of Work Package 2, Micro-credentials Observatory, which focuses on lifelong learning and innovative forms of certification.

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have affiliations with the organizations cited in the article, which did not interfere with the research methods, findings and presentation in any way.

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